

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABIN ANZAR bearing USN 6SU19CV001 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ACHUTH A bearing USN 6SU19CV002 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL PRAKASH M P bearing USN 6SU19CV003 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL RAGHAV bearing USN 6SU19CV004 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALAN SUNNY bearing USN 6SU19CV005 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSEEF MOTTAMMAL bearing USN 6SU19CV006 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE VV bearing USN 6SU19CV007 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DAYA SATHYAN bearing USN 6SU19CV008 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOUTHAM CHANDRA A bearing USN 6SU19CV009 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIBA FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU19CV010 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIBA PP bearing USN 6SU19CV011 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESLIN M M bearing USN 6SU19CV012 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN JAISON bearing USN 6SU19CV013 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LOYAL SHELLY bearing USN 6SU19CV014 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MINSHAB bearing USN 6SU19CV015 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MIZHAB V C bearing USN 6SU19CV016 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHAFID C S bearing USN 6SU19CV017 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHI P K bearing USN 6SU19CV018 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIMMEY GEORGE bearing USN 6SU19CV019 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NISHITH bearing USN 6SU19CV020 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RABEEH V V bearing USN 6SU19CV021 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAISA NAVAS bearing USN 6SU19CV022 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAVEENA R bearing USN 6SU19CV023 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROOPA NAIK bearing USN 6SU19CV024 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms S SREEREJ bearing USN 6SU19CV025 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMNAD M bearing USN 6SU19CV026 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHEIKH ZAHID AHMED bearing USN 6SU19CV027 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHUBHASHREE SHAILAJA SALIAN bearing USN 6SU19CV028 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREELAKSHMI SASIDHARAN bearing USN 6SU19CV029 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA PAVITHRAN bearing USN 6SU19CV030 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146